

SDN-Controlled Resource-Tailored Analytics for Healthcare IoT System

Sudip Misra, *Fellow, IEEE*, Saswati Pal, *Graduate Student Member, IEEE*, Nurzaman Ahmed, *Member, IEEE*, and Anandarup Mukherjee, *Member, IEEE*

Abstract—In this work, we propose *phSDN*, a programmable healthcare network architecture for resource-tailored management and on-demand allocation of analytic modules in IoT healthcare system. The identification, dynamic management of services, and fast analysis of healthcare data are a few challenges in existing remote healthcare monitoring devices. *phSDN* programs and reconfigures the resources and services, while updating the associated flow-rules in the data-plane of SDN architecture. It is especially useful in scenarios with intermittent or constrained network connectivity and/or device availability. The newly identified flows associated with different resources are explicitly considered, while forwarding services over the SDN network. The on-the-fly programmable services enable healthcare devices to provide resource-specific analytics. The programmability over services also allows unified control over the end-devices by reconfiguring on-the-fly vendor-specific heterogeneity of resource types. Our prototype of *phSDN* supports three different types of resources: (a) body temperature, (b) pulse rate, and (c) blood pressure. Experiments using our implementation shows that the proposed architecture minimizes the network response time by at least 43.87% and 78.4%, compared to the fog- and cloud-based approaches, respectively. The implemented system’s scalability is further evaluated using Mininet by considering latency, packet delivery ratio, and throughput, as the performance metrics.

Index Terms—Internet of Things, IoT, Software-Defined Network, SDN, Programmability, Healthcare IoT System.

I. INTRODUCTION

IoT-enabled diagnostic devices allow monitoring and analysis of patient’s physiological signals in real-time and, at a later time, via Web-based applications. These platforms are proving indispensable in situations requiring remote diagnostics, monitoring, and patient consultation, such as the COVID-19 pandemic. However, in any IoT-enabled healthcare ecosystem, heterogeneous resource control and resource-driven analytics management are the fundamental issues. For example, consider a scenario where a healthcare IoT system incorporates a set of heterogeneous resources (*i.e.*, nodes with variety of wearable sensors). The system includes one algorithm each for a resource to analyze the specific data, detect anomaly, and provide data-driven decision. For the IoT healthcare system to be scalable, it is necessary to support an increasing number of resources and the corresponding analytics without affecting its Quality of Service (QoS). Conventionally, IoT-based diagnostic devices lack facilities necessary for enabling on-the-fly

integration (*i.e.*, dynamic accommodation) of functionalities of new resources. While the existing healthcare IoT systems provide a unified platform for continuous monitoring and meaningful analysis of patient’s vitals’ complex characteristics, the heterogeneity of IoT resources and components demand an *on-the-fly* mechanism for reconfiguration of the services. The conventional networking approaches (*e.g.*, fog and cloud) facilitate the transmission of data to centralized repositories, which often witness increased network latency, computation time, and response time due to traffic congestion.

In this work, we propose a Software-defined Network (SDN)-controlled programmable healthcare network architecture – *phSDN*, to provide on-demand analysis of the physiological signals from newly allocated resources in an existing IoT-enabled diagnostic device, thereby enabling “*Analytics-on-the-Fly*”. The proposed solution “tailors” the existing services with the required analytics, dynamically. We prefer using the term *tailored* to driven, because analytics are not allocated based on resources. In contrast, the flow containing resource type is matched to the entries in a flow table. Based on the flow parameters, customized analytics is fetched and programmed to blend into the device functionality. This feature provides end-to-end QoS in terms of on-the-fly analytics. We briefly illustrate an instance for the proposed platform in Fig. 1. As

Fig. 1: Functional overview of the proposed architecture

depicted, we consider patients utilizing different diagnostic devices for ubiquitous monitoring. We integrate two distinct resources into two different devices. Consequently, the device updates its control data accordingly before transmitting it to the SDN switch, which wirelessly updates the information to the remote server. The remote server transfers relevant

Sudip Misra, Nurzaman Ahmed, and Anandarup Mukherjee are with Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur, India (e-mail: sudip_misra@yahoo.com).

Saswati Pal is with School of Nano-Science and Technology, Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur, India.

analytical modules and configuration files for the newly integrated resources to the SDN controller. The SDN controller then places the new flow-rules in the switch to distribute the analytic modules to be accommodated at the identified device.

SDN bridges the healthcare system and network providers' gap for updating, managing, and offering other benefits. However, the existing solutions are deficient in addressing the dynamic management of disparate resource-tailored services over heterogeneous IoT devices. Moreover, the cloud/fog-based analytic services commonly implemented in the contemporary healthcare IoT platforms incur huge latency due to their static architecture in terms of locations and communication networks. Programmability in the existing solutions is not suitable for the next-generation healthcare network in the sense that they are limited to flow-rule placement and reconfiguration only. The current controller fails to program devices at the extreme edge with a unit analytical module or a set of modules for faster and on-demand diagnostics. Accordingly, the network also fails to respond instantly as per the type of the resources. Moreover, programming such resources is still challenging due to the lack of an application programming interface (API) to support network, protocols, and devices heterogeneity. Therefore, a network-assisted and resource-tailored communication and computation system is crucial for smart healthcare.

In this paper, we propose *phSDN*, which identifies healthcare resources and programs network devices accordingly, for dynamic management of services and faster analysis. *phSDN* addresses the issues of heterogeneity and dynamic interpretation in a healthcare IoT ecosystem. The specific *contributions* of this paper are as follows:

- We propose *phSDN* to provide on-the-fly analysis of physiological signals monitored on a diagnostic device. The device is designed to enable quick integration and operation of new resources.
- We propose a resource-tailored reconfigurable diagnostic device to incorporate the configuration and functioning of new resources.
- We propose a resource-tailored programmable switch to assist on-demand analytics among several diagnostic devices.

II. RELATED WORKS

In this section, we discuss several works concerning SDN-based architecture for health-specific services, flow-rule management, and content-based flow-rules. A thorough analysis on different trends in healthcare IoT revealed that SDN technologies are essential to support QoS needs of IoT systems [1]. The SDN approach is employed in healthcare devices to essentially solve the issues of QoS requirements, heterogeneity, and security [2], [3]. To address the processing and computational constraints in healthcare IoT systems, the authors in [4] integrated SDN architecture in edge device to provide a secure framework. Several SDN-based architectures were proposed integrating fog computation and blockchain in IoT environments for intelligent management of the heterogeneous resources in the network [5]–[7]. Moreover, existing solutions

[8]–[10] are not suitable for supporting interoperability among the networks, vendors, and protocols.

The management of large-scale SDN architectures is performed using dynamic flow-rules, where the controller influences the behavior of network elements locally [11]. The dynamic rules involving both fixed and reconfigurable match fields enhance the flexibility and programmability of the SDN switches. However, the resulting traffic disruption, transmission interference, and packet losses in the network can be addressed using a priority-based flow mechanism [12]. This approach minimizes the volume of packet loss and disruption time, however, the control messages generated from flow command contributes to latency. To address the latency issues, approaches such as deep reinforcement learning based flow-rules [13] and filtering the traffic on controller-side [14] have been proposed.

The content-driven SDN architectures allow optimizing the network traffic, thereby enabling priority-wise resource handling and resource-based services [15]. The SDN controller interprets the content and forwards the flow-rules to the network switches. Other impactful approaches include priority-based flow-rules [16], incorporating dynamic traffic balancing with predictive and proactive controller [17], and reconfigurable edge nodes [18].

TABLE I: Summary of existing works

Work (Ref.)	On-the-fly Analytic	Content-based Programmability	Support of Heterogeneity	Provisioning Priority
[4], [19], [20]	✗	✗	✓	✗
[11], [12], [16]	✗	✗	✗	✓
[15], [18]	✗	✓	✓	✗
<i>phSDN</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓

With the growing number of IoT devices for the smart environments e.g., healthcare or home), the number of services is also increasing. In most cases, a single device uses multiple resources (e.g., temperature, humidity) for the required number of services. Existing works such as identification of services [21] and flows [22] show suitability for provisioning QoS. However, resource-specific QoS is important to be considered. With the advantages of SDN, this scheme proposes a network-assisted and resource-tailored communication and computation system for addressing the dynamic management services over heterogeneous IoT devices.

In Table II, we summarize the existing works based on the aspects compared to the proposed approach. The network devices utilized in the existing systems, such as gateways, routers, and switches, run complex and distributed control software, which are typically proprietary. Further, the existing SDN-based architectures lack heterogeneity, flexibility and low-latency communication, considering the content of flows, and the existing flow structure does not support the type of resources, which makes the network unaware of newer resources. Therefore, provisioning QoS for critical healthcare applications is challenging. Moreover, a considerable latency is incurred in cloud-based analysis for different healthcare-related decision making. Eventually, there emerges a need for on-the-fly programming of devices to incorporate dynamism in services without influencing real-time functioning.

III. SYSTEM DESIGN

The proposed *phSDN* system architecture consists of reconfigurable healthcare diagnostic devices, programmable SDN switches, SDN controller, and remote servers supporting Web applications. The diagnostic device is composed of heterogeneous resources attached to the patient's body to sense, collect, and analyze physiological data to provide predictive analysis of their vital parameters. These resources are associated with local controlling units, which are connected to a processing unit via different communication protocols, such as RS-232, Zigbee, WiFi, and 6LoWPAN.

Fig. 2: Service architecture of proposed *phSDN*

In *phSDN*, a pervasive programmable service is enabled, as depicted in Fig. 2. The segregated data and analysis therein are forwarded from the diagnostic device to the remote server via switches to offer web-based services. The diagnostic device is essentially designed to reconfigure itself whenever a new resource is connected by identifying the resource-type based on the header field of the packets incoming from the respective local controlling units. It transmits the physiological and control data to the SDN switches, which is programmed accordingly by the SDN controller. In order to facilitate the analytics for the newly introduced resources, the SDN controller identifies the newly initiated flow and places relevant rules in the switches. The switches programmed by the SDN controller forward the required analytical modules to the recognized destination accordingly.

Fig. 3: Overview of proposed Ryu-based *phSDN* Controller

Fig. 3 shows the architecture of the proposed *phSDN* controller. We modified the traditional Ryu controller [23] with a set of additional modules to support *phSDN*. We introduced the Analytic and Resource manager modules to manage and

program different analytic and resource-tailored tasks. These modules help in taking different resource-oriented decisions at the controller. The API manager handles the selection of API and parameters to be passed. To enable resource-tailored forwarding in the Openflow table, the match field of the table is added with an additional field named *Resource Type*, as shown in Fig. 4. The resource type field contains *version* and *name* sub-fields. The version indicates the unique standard of the particular resource, while the name displays its type. The *phSDN* architecture offers end-to-end infrastructure programmability as shown in Fig. 5 in two instances – resources and flow-rules which are discussed next.

A. Resource Programmability

The resource-tailored programming in *phSDN* helps in (i) solving heterogeneity by programming and reconfiguring sensor and actuator resources on-the-fly, and (ii) provisioning dynamic QoS. We propose a light-weight programmable protocol developed over the Constrained Application Protocol (CoAP), as illustrated in Algorithm 1. The proposed programming module and handshaking are represented in Fig. 5(a). We define additional control packet, Resource Programming Request (RPREq), which is initiated by the diagnostic device for programming a resource. Whenever the device detects any sensor or actuator activity, it requests the controller for resource registration through the RPREq packet. The programming operations – add, delete, and edit are identified by a unique ID. The device gives an update of the list of integrated resources, R_1, R_2, \dots, R_n in a periodic manner.

Considering the heterogeneous devices, communicating over different communication technologies, our initial task is to deploy the CoAP server module along with the additional functions for handling remote and real-time programming features. To support interoperability over vendor-specific heterogeneity, the proposed method modifies a resource. For example, the existing body temperature resource, *temperature* is modified to *temp* for unified analytic and flow management. The resource manager module in the controller maintains the list and takes decisions for future programming operations, such as placing flow-rule and analytic module.

Algorithm 1 Resource programming at diagnostic device

```

INPUT: Control packet
OUTPUT: Unified resource
PROCEDURE:
if New resource detected then
  Send control data to the Controller with RPREq
  Controller checks resources
  if Programming required then
    Send ACK
    Initiate programming for add/edit/delete
  else
    Send NACK
  end if
else
  Wait for control packet
end if

```

The proposed approach to accomplish the transfer of the analytical module is operated by the SDN controller, which periodically monitors the resource types from the incoming resource specific traffic flows. Upon successful extraction of

Ingress port	MAC DA	MAC SA	Ether type	VLAN ID	IP bits	IP src	IP dst	IP protocol	IP DSCP	TCP src	TCP dst	Resource type	
												Version	Name

Fig. 4: Table entry with additional match field for OpenFlow Switch

Fig. 5: End-to-end infrastructure programmability

resource types and flow category, it places the required flow-rules and checks the availability of analytical modules. If the module is not available as per the resource, it creates a new module and transfer it from the remote controller.

B. Flow-rule Programmability

We redefined a flow in the network, considering the resources and introduced a new field in the flow table and header to identify the proposed flow type. The *packet_in* header is modified to add resource version and name within the data field. Fig. 5(b) shows the switch to controller communication for a new packet coming from a diagnostic device. Once the resource name is known to the controller, the associated flow-rules are dynamically placed at the requested switch. The proposed flow placement scheme prioritizes the traffic dealing with the programmability of resources and analytics, as depicted in Algorithm 2. The proposed scheme uses a failure count to decide which flow to be processed first. For a failure in the process, the count value increases by 1. In the case of the same priority, the flow with the highest count value is processed first. The resource manager module in the controller keeps a record of all available healthcare resources for making future programming decisions. The record of the resource-specific analytics modules is managed by the Analytical Manager in the *phSDN* controller.

Algorithm 2 Resource-tailored priority flow placement

INPUT: Flows with priority
OUTPUT: Flow placement and forwarding
PROCEDURE:
 Classify flows with decreasing priority in the sequence: resource-based control, resource-based data, and standard flow
 Set priority
 Place flow-rule with priority
if Resource specific packet received **then**
 Check priority value in the table
 if Multiple priority flows detected **then**
 Process flow with highest priority value
 else
 Process flow as first come first serve basis
 end if
else
 Continue default actions
end if

Fig. 6: Communication technologies used in diagnostic device

IV. SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

We implemented the proposed programmable healthcare network architecture, *phSDN* in the laboratory set-up with a real-time diagnostic device prototype utilizing three different resources – body temperature, pulse rate, and blood pressure. The prototype contains a processor of 1 GB RAM and ARM Cortex with 4 computational cores, each with a clock cycle ranging from 700 MHz to 1.4 GHz. It incorporates 3 Wireless Body Area Network (WBAN) nodes, each with a non-invasive sensing device to fetch body temperature, pulse rate, and blood pressure from the subjects. The prototype supports an intuitive touchscreen-based user interface for users to view the real-time data recording. We utilized the real-time prototype to collect the physiological data from 16 healthy and 4 unhealthy subjects in the laboratory with age groups ranging from 20 – 40 years. The unhealthy subjects exhibited fever and high blood pressure. Prior to conducting human trials, we provided a demonstration of the operation of the device to the subjects. To validate the collected data, we acquired the same readings from the clinical-grade devices simultaneously. The different resources (sensors) use heterogeneous communication technologies – RS-232, Zigbee, WiFi, and 6LoWPAN for transmitting the physiological data to the processing unit, as shown in Fig. 6. The processing unit collects sensitive data from multiple on-body resources simultaneously, processes them to obtain significant insights into the patient’s health, and predicts any unforeseen condition. In particular, we utilized two stages of implementation, which we discuss next.

A. Network Testbed

The *phSDN* architecture is implemented on a real-time testbed with a developed diagnostic device with several resources. The SDN controller is hosted in Intel[®] Xeon[®] Gold 5118 Processor with 12 CPU and 2.30 GHz frequency. We utilized

Dell EMC Switch for OpenFlow-based core networking. The core of the diagnostic device is a Raspberry Pi connected to resources via heterogeneous communication modules, as illustrated in Fig. 6. The core processing unit supports Open vSwitch to route the control data, physiological data, and the pertinent analysis to the SDN core network. The SDN switch initially checks the flow table to identify the flow-rule entry corresponding to the incoming resource type. Upon successful identification, it forwards the data to a remote server for the clinician or the user to assess the information via Web-based services. On the other hand, if the switch fails to locate the flow entry, then it sends a query packet to the SDN controller. The controller places new flow-rules at the designated switch and reprograms it with the appropriate analytical module.

B. Mininet Emulation

We emulated the prototype environment in Mininet [24] to evaluate the scalability of *phSDN* considering tree topology with multiple hosts and switches. The emulation in Mininet allows for a qualitative evaluation ensuring the applicability and verify the reliability of deploying the proposed concept to an expensive real network. Moreover, emulating the proposed concept in large network offers to manage any improper configurations thus avoiding unforeseen glitches. The experiments were run until all the flows were routed to the destination while the generation duration for each flow is kept as 10 seconds. Further, we considered that the flows generate traffic at a different rate. We utilized the Ryu controller and Open vSwitch supporting OpenFlow protocol. Ryu controller manages higher traffic rate (flow rules) for improved and intelligent network management. It uses protocols to notify switches where to send the packets. Open vSwitch allows network automation by supporting configuration and migration between network states. Further, we used the D-ITG generator to generate traffic flows and evaluated the network performance in terms of flows and switches [25].

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

We evaluated the implemented *phSDN* by running experiments with the developed diagnostic device. We utilized Mininet to emulate the entire network architecture depicting programmable resources, flow-rules, and analytical modules. We use a on-the-fly resource programming approach to place an analytical module on the targeted devices to take decision on the extreme edge. We compare *phSDN* with fog and cloud-based placement of analytical module for task execution on a first come first serve basis. The scalability of *phSDN* is evaluated by varying several parameters:

- 1) *Diagnostic devices*: The proposed network architecture is implemented with three diagnostic devices with heterogeneous resources. Each of these 3 devices has 3 different types of resources – body temperature, pulse rate, and blood pressure. Additionally, we consider dynamic integration of two different sets of resources – ECG and blood oxygen saturation for devices *D1* and *D2*, respectively. For the devices *D1* and *D2*, we integrate 3-lead ECG sensor and pulse oximeter sensor, respectively.

We measure the R-R interval on the ECG to compute the heart rate of the subject. The pulse oximeter sensor measures the blood oxygen saturation level as well as the heart rate. We validate the heart rate computed from R-R interval of ECG with the heart rate data fetched from the pulse oximeter sensor.

- 2) *Flows*: *phSDN* considers the flows as per the type of the resources. For e.g., similar rules are followed for same type of resource (say, body temperature) for the network. We vary the number of flows incoming from the SDN controller to the switches from 500 – 4000 to evaluate the effect of large flow (traffic) on the network performance in terms of network latency, throughput, and packet delivery ratio.
- 3) *Available switches*: We increase the number of switches to evaluate its effect on network latency and packet loss. We vary the number of switches from 5 – 15. We consider that the SDN controller can support up to a maximum of 15 switches for QoS provision.

The performance of *phSDN* architecture is evaluated using the metrics discussed below.

Fig. 7: Time taken for computation and communication

A. Computation Time

The computation time is measured as the total time incurred by the device in acquiring the physiological data from the resources and computing the analytics for the data. Fig. 7(a) depicts the computation time for different diagnostic devices. It is observed that the computation time decreases for the devices with a lesser number of resources. This behavior is attributed to the heterogeneous communication technologies used to establish the connection between the local unit controlling the resource and the processing unit of the device. Further, different resources have varying sizes of configuration files and analytical modules. This leads to the lowest computation time incurred by device *D3* since it includes three types of resources. In contrast, devices *D1* and *D2* have four types of resources each, with a larger configuration file for the additional resource in device *D1*.

B. Interoperability

The resources utilized in the diagnostic devices are connected to its processing unit via 1-hop distance from heterogeneous communication technologies based on different protocols. The communication technologies with varying data transmission protocols used are RS-232 serial communication protocol,

Fig. 8: Component response time

Fig. 9: Network latency in diagnostic devices

Fig. 10: End-to-end network latency

Fig. 11: Network throughput vs no. of switches

IEEE 802.15.4-based 6LoWPAN and ZigBee protocol, and IEEE 802.11-based ESP8266 WiFi protocol. From Fig. 7(b), it is observed that serial communication is fastest, followed by IEEE 802.15.4-based protocols. Although both the IEEE 802.15.4-based protocols have the same data rate, 6LoWPAN is faster than ZigBee since it employs IPv6 packets for data transmission. Interestingly, the WiFi takes more time for data transmission as compared to other technologies. This behavior is attributed to the larger packet size of the resource connected via the ESP8266 module. Considering the requirements of technology, protocol, and system, we create a software module and deploy it to the devices, which is controllable via API from the SDN controller. This addresses the heterogeneity issue in terms of technology as well as protocol. The proposed programmability over the resources resolves the vendor-specific heterogeneity by unifying their types.

C. Component Response Time

The proposed *phSDN* network architecture involves three key components – diagnostic device, SDN switch, and SDN controller. The component response time is computed as the time interval between a component receiving a request and acknowledging the results accordingly. Fig. 8 represents the response time obtained for different key components, which is influenced by the factors, such as data rate, payload size, processing speed, communication speed, and type of resources. The diagnostic device response time T_D , as shown in Fig. 8(a) is measured as the duration of time taken in sending a request for an analytic module for a new resource and receiving the corresponding module from the controller as computed below:

$$T_D = t_{gen} + t_{queue} + t_{pro} + t_{assign} \quad (1)$$

where t_{gen} is the time taken in generating the request packets, t_{queue} is the time incurred in the queue to reach the controller, t_{pro} is the time taken by the controller to initiate the processing for the request, and t_{assign} is the time interval during which the controller transmits the analytic module to its destination. The parameter t_{queue} is influenced by the interference from the higher priority requests and is computed as, $t_{queue} = \frac{l_{queue} + N_r}{\alpha}$. The parameter l_{queue} is the length of the queue, N_r is the number of requests with higher priority, and α is the arrival rate of packets. Considering that the controller transmits its traffic in slots, t_{assign} is denoted as a product of the number of slots η_s taken and the duration of each slot t_s , such that $t_{assign} = \eta_s \times t_s$. In Fig. 8(b), we show the switch response time T_S , which is obtained by the time taken for receiving the new control data from the diagnostic device and transmitting the packet to the controller, expressed as $T_S = t_{gen} + t_{queue}$ as discussed in Eq. 1. The controller response time T_C is obtained by the duration it takes to receive the flow request from the switch and places the corresponding flow-rule, denoted by $T_C = t_{pro} + t_{assign}$ (Refer Eq. 1). It is observed that the response time varies according to the configuration file size, which is higher for *D1*. This is because device *D1* consists of resources with greater payload requiring a larger configuration file as compared to device *D2*. Additionally, both devices, *D1* and *D2*, incorporate more resources than the device *D3*.

D. Network Latency

Fig. 9 depicts the network latency, which is measured as the time taken for the resource-tailored analytics to reach the diagnostic devices across the network. The SDN controller intelligently takes decision considering the priority of

Fig. 12: Packet Delivery Ratio

incoming requests and dynamically places the flow-rules at the switches. We observe that the network latency increases as the number of flows increases since the queuing of flows incurs a significant amount of delay. In Fig. 10, we present the end-to-end network latency for *phSDN* compared with fog- and cloud-based computing. As depicted in the figure, for 1000 flows, *phSDN* minimizes the end-to-end latency by at least 43.87% and 78.4%, compared to the fog- and cloud-based approaches, respectively. In particular, the network is more congested in the fog- and cloud-based approaches and hence the increased latency. The congestion in traffic increases for a greater number of flows and hence the delay in service.

E. Network Throughput

We compute the bandwidth utilization by the transmitted packets with a varying number of flows and an increasing number of switches, as illustrated in Fig. 11. The network throughput is computed as the effective bandwidth usage while transmitting data from the SDN controller to all the diagnostic devices in a network. It is expressed as $\mathcal{T} = P \times \eta_p$, where P refers to the probability of successful transmission of packets, and η_p is the total number of packets being delivered to the destination. It is observed that the network throughput increases exponentially with the increase in the number of flows since the traffic in the network increases. We also observe that a higher number of flows and switches offer traffic congestion. Nevertheless, it provides the necessary dynamic and intelligent QoS.

F. Packet Delivery Ratio

We compute the packet delivery ratio (PDR) as the ratio of the number of received packets to the total number of transmitted packets. Fig. 12 shows the PDR for varying numbers of packets, flows, and switches. We observe that *phSDN* is reliable with a maximum of 0.974 PDR for 50 packets and 100 number of flows, which decreases with an increase in the number of packets and flows as shown in Fig. 12(a). We notice a decrease in PDR with an increasing number of switches revealed in Figs. 12(b), and 12(c). This behavior is attributed to interference from other sources and traffic congestion resulting in the dropping of packets. Another possible reason is larger queuing time in the network resulting in eventual packet drops.

Fig. 13: Effect of priority on network latency and PDR

G. Priority-aware Flow Processing

In Fig. 13, we represent the effect of priority on the end-to-end network latency and the PDR. We consider 1000 packets each of size $1kB$ for individual flow to generate traffic. The result illustrates that the average latency is less for flows with priority than the non-priority flow-rules. Further, an increased number of flows shows a similar trend. This is because the flows with priority are executed with the utmost importance. In the case of PDR, we observe that more packets are lost in priority-aware processing of flow-rules with respect to the non-priority processing. We attribute this behavior to the queuing disruption resulting from heavy traffic in the network. It is observed that flow-rules with no priority support a higher PDR.

The proposed scheme takes different healthcare decisions from the extreme edge of the network, reducing critical data sharing and activity with the cloud and third parties. Therefore, the proposed scheme preserves the privacy of patients and other medical-related information upto a certain extent.

TABLE II: Comparison of *phSDN* with existing works.

Work (Ref.)	Comp. Time	Response Time	Interoperability	Throughput	PDR	Latency/Delay	Energy
Sood <i>et al.</i> [3]	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗
Li <i>et al.</i> [4]	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗
Latif <i>et al.</i> [5]	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓
Ren <i>et al.</i> [6]	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗
Roy <i>et al.</i> [7]	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓
<i>phSDN</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗

H. Comparison of *phSDN*

phSDN is a programmable network architecture for on-demand allocation of analytic modules in IoT healthcare system. In Table II, we present a comparison of the performance metrics evaluated in the recent works on SDN-IoT network and *phSDN*. The work in [3] proposed a SDN-IoT architecture considering QoS and security. They evaluated the response time, service time, flow arrival time, and throughput for the proposed approach. The authors in [4] proposed a secured SDN-based edge computing healthcare IoT system. They evaluated the proposed scheme in terms of response time, PDR, throughput, and delay. The works on integrated blockchain and SDN [5], [6] evaluated the throughput, PDR, delay, and energy requirements. The authors in [7] evaluated delay incurred and energy consumption. On the other hand, *phSDN* evaluates the network parameters, such as computation time, response time, interoperability, latency, throughput, and PDR. Since *phSDN* is implemented on a real-time testbed in a laboratory setup with stable power supplies, we do not evaluate the energy consumption by the network components.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this work, we proposed an SDN-controlled programmable healthcare network architecture, *phSDN* to allocate *on-the-fly* analytics to the end devices. The reconfiguration and programmability is considered at three stages – resource-based, flow-rule-based, and analytics-based. It is implemented in real-time on a device consisting of three resources – body temperature, pulse rate, and blood pressure. Two different sets of resources, ECG and blood oxygen saturation, are integrated to test *phSDN*'s efficacy. We evaluated *phSDN* on a large-scale using Mininet, which highlights that the architecture efficiently handles on-the-fly analytics without inducing additional network delays. Our approach helps to place an analytic module in the end devices as per the type of sensor or actuator resources or change them dynamically whenever required. At the same time, an SDN-enabled network makes a flow and resource programming approach easier.

In the future, we plan to extend this work to include fault-tolerance and robustness as these are critical aspects of any healthcare IoT ecosystem.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the funding support from INAE (Sanction letter no. INAE/121/AKF, Dt. 13-02-2019) for executing parts of this work. The authors are grateful to the Institute Ethical Committee, IIT Kharagpur (Approval letter no. IIT/SRIC/DR/2019, Dt. 29-11-2019) for providing ethical clearance required to conduct trials on human.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. H. Kashani, M. Madanipour, M. Nikravan, P. Asghari, and E. Mahdipour, "A systematic review of IoT in healthcare: Applications, techniques, and trends," *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, vol. 192, p. 103164, 2021.
- [2] S. Badotra, D. Nagpal, S. N. Panda, S. Tanwar, and S. Bajaj, "IoT-enabled healthcare network with SDN," in *2020 8th International Conference on Reliability, Infocom Technologies and Optimization (Trends and Future Directions)(ICRITO)*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 38–42.
- [3] K. Sood, K. K. Karmakar, S. Yu, V. Varadharajan, S. R. Pokhrel, and Y. Xiang, "Alleviating heterogeneity in SDN-IoT networks to maintain QoS and enhance security," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 7, no. 7, pp. 5964–5975, 2019.
- [4] J. Li, J. Cai, F. Khan, A. U. Rehman *et al.*, "A secured framework for SDN-based edge computing in IoT-enabled healthcare system," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 135 479–135 490, 2020.
- [5] S. A. Latif, F. B. X. Wen *et al.*, "AI-empowered, blockchain and SDN integrated security architecture for IoT network of cyber physical systems," *Computer Communications*, vol. 181, pp. 274–283, 2022.
- [6] J. Ren, J. Li, H. Liu, and T. Qin, "Task offloading strategy with emergency handling and blockchain security in SDN-empowered and fog-assisted healthcare IoT," *Tsinghua Science and Technology*, vol. 27, no. 4, pp. 760–776, 2021.
- [7] C. Roy, R. Saha, S. Misra, and D. Niyato, "Soft-Health: Software-defined Fog Architecture for IoT Applications in Healthcare," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 9, no. 3, 2021.
- [8] M. O. Farooq, I. Wheelock, and D. Pesch, "IoT-Connect: An Interoperability Framework for Smart Home Communication Protocols," *IEEE Consumer Electronics Magazine*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 22–29, 2019.
- [9] N. Pathak, A. Mukherjee, and S. Misra, "Reconfigure and Reuse: Interoperable Wearables for Healthcare IoT," in *IEEE Conference on Computer Communications Workshops (INFOCOM)*, 2020, pp. 20–29.
- [10] S. Mukherjee, S. Elias *et al.*, "An applications interoperability model for heterogeneous internet of things environments," *Computers & Electrical Engineering*, Elsevier, vol. 64, pp. 163–172, 2017.
- [11] Q. Wei, D. Perez-Caparrros, and A. Hecker, "Dynamic flow rules in software defined networks," in *Fifth European Workshop on Software-Defined Networks (EWSN)*. IEEE, 2016, pp. 25–30.
- [12] B.-H. Oh, S. Vural *et al.*, "Priority-based flow control for dynamic and reliable flow management in SDN," *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 1720–1732, 2018.
- [13] E. H. Bouzidi, A. Outtagarts, and R. Langar, "Deep reinforcement learning application for network latency management in software defined networks," in *IEEE GLOBECOM*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 1–6.
- [14] S. Deng, X. Gao, Z. Lu, Z. Li, and X. Gao, "DoS vulnerabilities and mitigation strategies in software-defined networks," *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, Elsevier, vol. 125, pp. 209–219, 2019.
- [15] A. Chanda, C. Westphal, and D. Raychaudhuri, "Content based traffic engineering in software defined information centric networks," in *IEEE INFOCOM WORKSHOPS*. IEEE, 2013, pp. 357–362.
- [16] B. Zhao, J. Zhao *et al.*, "RuleTailor: Optimizing Flow Table Updates in OpenFlow Switches With Rule Transformations," *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 1581–1594, 2019.
- [17] A. Montazerolghaem and M. H. Yaghmaee, "Load-balanced and QoS-aware Software-defined Internet of Things," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 3323–3337, 2020.
- [18] T. Rahman, X. Yao, G. Tao, H. Ning, and Z. Zhou, "Efficient edge nodes reconfiguration and selection for the Internet of Things," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 19, no. 12, pp. 4672–4679, 2019.
- [19] M. Cicioğlu and A. Çalhan, "SDN-based wireless body area network routing algorithm for healthcare architecture," *ETRI Journal, Wiley Online Library*, vol. 41, no. 4, pp. 452–464, 2019.
- [20] A. C. Baktir, C. Tunca, A. Ozgovde, G. Salur, and C. Ersoy, "SDN-based multi-tier computing and communication architecture for pervasive healthcare," *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 56 765–56 781, 2018.
- [21] N. Zhang, "Service discovery and selection based on dynamic qos in the internet of things," *Complexity*, vol. 2021, 2021.
- [22] N. Ahmed and S. Misra, "Collaborative Flow-Identification Mechanism for Software-Defined Internet of Things," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 3457–3464, 2022.
- [23] "Framework community: Ryu SDN framework," *Online*. <http://osrg.github.io/ryu>, 2015.
- [24] B. Lantz, B. Heller, and N. McKeown, "A network in a laptop: rapid prototyping for software-defined networks," in *Proceedings of the 9th ACM SIGCOMM Workshop on Hot Topics in Networks*, 2010, pp. 1–6.
- [25] A. Botta, A. Dainotti, and A. Pescapé, "A tool for the generation of realistic network workload for emerging networking scenarios," *Computer Networks*, Elsevier, vol. 56, no. 15, pp. 3531–3547, 2012.